

THE IMPACT OF ILLUSTRATIONS ON DEVELOPING EFL STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING

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ABSTRACT

The following article deals with the significance of illustrations on acquiring the right mind set and skills of EFL students. Illustrations such as pictures, diagrams, images and figures are considered as basic elements to develop criticism for learners. General understanding of the role of illustrations to develop EFL students' critical thinking, its great significance in teaching productive and receptive skills such as writing, speaking, reading and listening is analyzed effectively. It is clarified with examples about how illustrations support students master the interrelated skills. The role, types and significance of illustrations are highlighted in this article.

INTRODUCTION. In this developing period, traditional teaching aids such as course books, activity books, etc., have no longer great influence on learners. The benefits of illustrations and pictures, their alignment with the way the modern skill desires and expects to be taught, meet the increasing demand of students intent on developing critical thinking skills such as strong communication abilities, problem-solving, leadership and decision-making adaptability, and interpersonal skills. Indeed, pictures and images are so important learning tools to develop critical thinking. Adult learners, learners of all ages, are far more likely to remember pictures, visuals than words. An estimated 80 to 90 percent of the information we received is accessed through our vision, according to the Harvard business review. This supplies students with real cultural information of the target language and give chance to synthesize their culture and other cultures.

The benefits of using pictures in the language classroom have been researched and asserted by scholars over the years. The various approaches to language teaching have used images as a main tool in the language acquisition. It is mentioned that pictures as a tool that can improve the teaching and learning process through the use of them in order to develop critical thinking effectively. Furthermore, it made clear reference to how students and teachers are benefited in EFL classrooms. Following pictures are going to be alluded in the sense of how they help in the development of students' critical thinking skills.

The overview of studies carried out to prove the importance of visuals in foreign language acquisition have helped to state the hypothesis in this research paper. The researchers mentioned here have claimed that visuals help to enhance the language

teaching, as well as students' comprehension of the new input. Pictures also clarify the meaning of words and messages, help in memorizing new vocabulary, and in gaining students attention.

Indeed, a well-developed set of critical thinking skills builds self-empowerment and confidence. It enables you to efficiently gather knowledge, quickly process information and intelligently analyze data. Armed with critical thinking tools, you will be able to confidently adapt to most issues in life or work. At the present time, the teaching of English language must respond according to the development of updated teaching techniques. It is known that learners need extra instruction for them to understand better contents, and comprehend a second language. When teaching English, educators must find ways to exemplify and clarify contents to reach different kinds of learners. For this reason, the design and management of visual aids take an important role for the development of linguistic skills in the target language inside the EFL classroom. In general, it is recommended to utilize numerous illustrations to develop critical thinking of students and they give chance to memorize and comprehend new topic easily during the lessons. It is one of the most efficient ways to use appropriate pictures in activities related to theme in teaching language skills in foreign language.

It is better to remind our president's ideas about development the society in this place. "The Uzbekistan's Development Strategy for 2017 – 2021" which is to be implemented in 5 stages, each of which provides for approval of a separate annual State program in accordance with a declared name of the year, can be an example for the attempts to develop the society. The republic could only have sustained development and modernity if the people have the knowledge and expertise gained by having the opportunity to education at all levels right from junior school to higher education level. It is emphasized in the branch 4.4 "Development of education and science" in the Priority areas of development of the social sphere "implementing targeted measures aimed at strengthening the material – technical base of educational institutions through construction, reconstruction and repair, equipping with modern teaching and laboratory equipment, computers, teaching aids".¹

Activities carried out in our country on improving all links in the sphere of education and upbringing – the system of preschool, school, secondary special and higher education, construction of new and reconstruction of existing educational institutions will give its results in formation of young generation as harmoniously developed individuals.

It is obvious that it may be complicated to teach foreign language without illustrations and pictures. Visual aids, when integrated into the lesson plan through media, attract students' attention to the topic presented in the class, enhance and facilitate comprehension of grammar and language, develop critical thinking, increase students' motivation, as well as help students to memorize the new vocabulary and structures. Apart from being an excellent tool to improve the language acquisition, the use of visual in the classroom provides a more meaningful context for the students. All these factors lead students to become more active and communicative members of the class group.

¹ Sh. M. Mirziyoyev. "On Uzbekistan's Development strategy". Tashkent, 2017.

Illustrations such as pictures, graphs, drawings or dynamic videos are often designed to facilitate learning and have a positive influence. From the learning and instruction point of view, the effectiveness of the visual information is concerned with cognitive learning and retention. Furthermore, the performance criteria of learning materials are mainly focused on comprehension and recall.

Methods of investigation: To gain aimed results the following methods are used:

1. Critical study
2. Theoretical and linguistic analysis
3. Quantitative method;
4. Descriptive method.

It learns the effectiveness of utilizing appropriate illustrations in developing critical thinking while teaching language, reveals the types of visuals which can be used during the lessons, studies the features that should be considered while using various pictures related to new topic and identifies the significance of illustrations at schools in Uzbekistan in teaching a foreign language.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, illustrations are defined to facilitate the learning process and to improve the outcomes in the language classroom. The application of pictures in EFL classrooms implies several issues to take into consideration in order to address students with different characteristics. They denote to something which is used by teachers or students to facilitate the language learning process. However, the role of the teacher is fundamental in this process; it is the teacher's responsibility to conduct the learning and to deliver the necessary tools. In this sense, visual aids contribute considerably in this process and in other scenery as an oral communication process. In short, illustrations are so important to address students' critical thinking skills and their diverse capacities. Consequently, their learning process is improved and strengthened.

References:

1. Sh. M. Mirziyoyev. "On Uzbekistan's Development strategy". Tashkent, 2017.
2. Canning-Wilson, C. (1998) "Visual support and language teaching". TESOL Arabia News, Vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 3-4.
3. Carney, R.N and Levin, J.R. (2002) "Pictorial Illustrations still Improve students" Learning from Text' Educational Psychology Review, Vol. 14, no. 1, March.
4. Clark, R.C and Lyons, C. (2004) Graphics for Learning: Proven Guidelines for Planning, Designing, and Evaluation visuals in Training Materials, San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer.
5. Evans, V. and Green, M. (2006) "Cognitive Linguistics: An Introduction." Oxford University Press.
6. Levin, J.R and Mayer, R.E. (1993) 'Understanding illustrations in text', in Brinton, B.K., Woodward, A. and Brinkley, M. (eds.). Learning from textbooks, Erlbaum, pp 95-113
7. Nation, I. & Newton, J. (2009). Teaching ESL/EFL Listening and Speaking. NY: Routledge.
8. www.google.com
9. www.language.ru